

Standing in for Ricardo Peres
(Imperial College London)

Neutrino Physics with XLZD

NuPhys2026, King's College London,
07/01/26

Jim Dobson, King's College London

Liquid Xenon Time Projection Chambers

Secondary ionisation signal (S2)

Key features: excellent charge/light yields, $\sigma \propto A^2$, lack of long-lived problematic radioisotopes, fiducialisation \rightarrow highly scalable.

Leading Dark Matter (DM) technology above a -few GeV

ZEPLIN-III/XENON10

12 kg (7 kg)

2008

XENON100

62 kg (34 kg)

2013

LUX

250 kg (100 kg)

2016

PANDAX-II

580 kg (362 kg)

2017

XENON1T

2,000 kg (1,042 kg)

2018

PANDAX-4t/LUX-ZEPLIN/XENON-nT

7,000 kg (5,600 kg)

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Multi-tonne-scale Xe targets → now also neutrino detectors (low threshold, CEvNS)

PANDAX-4t/LUX-ZEPLIN/XENON-nT

7,000 kg (5,600 kg)

2022-27

The XLZD detector concept

- Builds on mature technology → combines best of XENON, LUX-ZEPLIN & DARWIN R&D
- ~factor 2 linear scale-up → manageable technical challenges
- Eventual 60-80 tonne active natural LXe target
- Two arrays 3" low-background PMTs (2362 tubes total)
 - Other sensors under study
- Drift field 240-290 V/cm
- Highly (VUV) reflective PTFE walls
- Radiopure material selection and background mitigation (active veto, online reduction, analysis)

XLZD Design book: [Eur. Phys. J. C \(2025\) 85: 1192](#)

A Dark Matter and Rare Event Physics Observatory

Ultra-low BG + large exposure + high dynamic range → broad physics programme

Dark Matter:

- WIMP
- Sub-GeV
- Inelastic
- Axion-like particles
- Planck mass
- Dark photons

Neutrino nature:

- Neutrinoless double beta decay
- Neutrino magnetic moment
- Double electron capture

Supernovae:

- Early alert
- Supernova neutrinos
- Multi-messenger astrophysics

Solar:

- pp neutrinos
- Solar metallicity
- ${}^7\text{Be}$, ${}^8\text{B}$, hep

Whitepaper: LXe observatory for DM and ν -physics

[J Aalbers et al 2023 J. Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys. 50 013001](#)

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Focus of this talk → neutrino physics opportunities

Neutrinoless double beta decay with ^{136}Xe

- Natural abundance of ^{136}Xe (8.9%) (could choose to later enrich/deplete)
- $Q_{\beta\beta} = 2458$ keV
- Exploit excellent self-shielding → search in inner 11 tonne FV (~ 1 tonne ^{136}Xe)
- 10^7 reduction in background events in detector centre
- XLZD $0\nu\beta\beta$ sensitivity paper: [*J.Phys.G* 52 \(025\) 4, 045102](#)

Neutrinoless double beta decay backgrounds

Important backgrounds in region of interest (2.46 MeV): high energy gammas; cosmogenic ^{137}Xe ; ν -e ^8B neutrinos; ^{222}Rn emanation:

J. Aalbers et al, J.Phys.G 52 (2025) 4, 045102

Neutrinoless double beta decay sensitivity

Assuming: 0.1 uBq/kg ^{222}Rn , achievable improvements in material radiopurity, 0.65% energy resolution, 99.99% Bi-Po tagging.

Cover the IO parameter space at 3σ . Exclude part of NO:

Supernova neutrino detection

- For Type II SN, ~99% of the gravitational energy of the progenitor is emitted as neutrinos
- Neutrino energies: ~10 MeV
- Burst event: <10 s

SN neutrinos precede the light wave by minutes to hours

Early warning to the astronomical community.

R. Lang et al., Phys. Rev. D 94 (10), 103009 (2016)

jim.dobson@kcl.ac.uk - NuPhys2026

Supernova neutrino detection

- Main channel is CEvNS → flavour independent
 - Useful for reconstructing the neutralisation burst (suppressed in the CC channel due to oscillations)
- Low energy search ~few keV recoil energies
 - Low thresholds key
 - Need to handle single and few-electron backgrounds

R. Lang et al., Phys. Rev. D 94 (10), 103009 (2016)

Supernova neutrino detection significance

XENON collaboration, plot courtesy Ricardo Peres

- Complementary information c.f. dedicated neutrino telescopes
- Flavour blind \rightarrow measure average energy of all flavours and constrain total explosion energy
- Expect 3-5 sigma sensitive beyond SMC
- No directionality but enough time resolution for light-curve reconstruction (distance/stats limited)

Solar nu physics

Backgrounds for DM search—also an opportunity to measure with a low-threshold detector

Solar neutrinos - electron recoils (ν -e)

Channel is \sim few-100 keV electron recoils

For pp neutrinos \rightarrow expect $O(20 \text{ cts/tonne/year}) \rightarrow$ many 1000s events for $600 \cdot \text{t} \cdot \text{y}$ exposure $\rightarrow < 5\%$ precision of P_{ee} survival rate

J. Aalbers et al, Eur.Phys.J.C 85 (2025) 10, 1192

Astrophysical neutrinos - nuclear recoils (CEvNS)

- Coherent Elastic Neutrino-Nucleus Scattering predicted by D. Freedman (1974)
- First observed by COHERENT with spallation neutrons (2017)
- At low momentum transfer the coherent process is enhanced
 - Cross section scales with number of neutrons: $\sigma \propto N^2$
 - The signature is a (very) small nuclear recoil

Science 357,1123-1126 (2017)

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dE_R} = \frac{G_F^2 M}{4\pi} Q_W^2 \left(1 - \frac{ME_R}{2E_\nu^2} - \frac{E_R}{E_\nu} \right) [F(q^2)]^2$$

$$Q_W^2 = [Z(1 - 4 \sin^2(\theta_W)) - N]$$

Astrophysical neutrinos - nuclear recoils (CEvNS)

- Following results by XENON-nT [Phys. Rev. Lett. 133, 191002 (2024)] and PandaX-nT [Phys. Rev. Lett. 133, 191001 (2024)]
- Now have 4.5σ for ^8B seen in LUX-ZEPLIN in 5.7 tonne.year exposure [arxiv.org/2512.08065]

- With XLZD +300-tonne year exposure can test ν_e survival probability and low/high-metallicity standard solar models

In summary

- LXe technology is mature and scalable
- Ambitious plans for a 60-80 tonne LXe-based rare event search observatory
- Mass allows for broad ν -physics programme
 - Competitive $0\nu\beta\beta$ sensitivity
 - Solar, SN and other ν -searches
- Leverages low-threshold and flavour blind CEvNS capability
- At the design phase → site selection in 2026 → operation in the 2030s

